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Climate Futures are Political Futures: Integrating Political Development Into the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs)

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Abstract

The Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) are the key scenarios used by the climate change research community for evaluating mitigation pathways and the costs and challenges of meeting the Paris goals as well as climate risks along these different pathways. Despite ample evidence that political factors – such as institutional strength, rule of law-based accountability, and violent conflict – are critical determinants of climate action and vulnerability to climate hazards, the SSPs currently acknowledge but do not include quantified political factors systematically. We argue that without integrating political development into socioeconomic scenarios for climate mitigation and adaptation, projections are unlikely to reflect the challenges from climate change nor provide serious guidance on the political barriers to climate action. Consequently, models under-estimate climate risks. It is of immediate concern to extend the SSPs by integrating relevant political factors. In this paper, we examine how political development co-evolves with and influences climate futures, covering a wide range of issues from institutions to armed conflict. We showcase existing quantified political factors and the state of the art of the research on political futures, which may inform current SSP update processes. By outlining a research agenda to explore opportunities to integrate the co-evolution of political factors with socioeconomic, technical, and environmental developments as integral part of scenarios, we aim to contribute to the building blocks for a new generation of climate scenarios.

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1. INTRODUCTION¹

Tackling global climate change necessitates reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions required for the temperature goals of the Paris Agreement (Mora et al., 2018). Hence, countries must make decisions on how to distribute the unequal benefits and burdens of climate mitigation and adaptation. This *collective* climate action is increasingly threatened by geostrategic tensions and rise of violent conflicts (Davies et al., 2022); a wave of autocratization accompanied by polarization and disinformation (Wiebrecht et al., 2023); and the deterioration of rule-based multilateralism (Rodrik & Walt, 2022). Political factors play a vital role for our possible climate futures.²

Despite a generic appreciation of the importance of political factors (Bernauer, 2013; Brutschin et al., 2021; Jewell & Cherp, 2020; Trutnevyte et al., 2019), most scenario-based analyses of future socioeconomic developments and climate mitigation/adaptation do not integrate measures of them systematically or quantitatively. Critically, the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) – the five core societal scenarios – build on political factors but their elaboration is limited and not consistent. Hence, long-term implications of alternative political trajectories on climate action are critically understudied and challenges to climate action therefore probably severely underestimated.

This paper argues that the SSPs should be adapted to better represent political development that enable or limit action on climate change. By political development, we refer to three complementary dimensions: characteristics of national political institutions (e.g., accountability and inclusion; hereafter referred to as 'political regime'), the quality/capacity of these institutions ('governance'), and violent conflict. We suggest two entry points into the existing climate scenario framework:

- Validating and enhancing existing narratives in the SSPs with theoretical insights building on robust empirical evidence on how political development shapes adaptation and mitigation.
- Incorporating quantified political factors into the SSPs and integrating them into the analysis of mitigation and adaptation action.

Political development has an international dimension (global governance), which includes geopolitical aspects, multilateralism, and ideological dynamics. Yet, this paper focuses on domestic political institutions because it is in that space that collectively binding decisions are taken and implemented and international decisions are adopted and translated into actionable policies. The quantified SSP framework also is built around country-level characteristics.

In response to calls from climate modeling communities to incorporate political factors in scenarios (Brutschin & Andrijevic, 2022; Davidson et al., 2024), this paper thus aims to contribute to ongoing SSP update processes. It is part of an iterative process that started at the first Scenario Forum (SF) 2019 at the University of Denver. Authors of the present paper then invested in community-building to enable such an effort and the integration of political development in the SF 2022 in Laxenburg and in two workshops with modeling communities and political scientists in 2022 and 2023. Given the relative dearth of studies that could form the basis of a meta-analysis and model comparisons, this paper offers a conceptual foundation and launches a research agenda, informed by leading political science research, outlining how to integrate quantified political factors in the SSPs.

2. POLITICAL DEVELOPMENT MATTERS FOR CLIMATE MITIGATION AND ADAPTATION

The IPCC Sixth Assessment Report assesses “governance”, “institutional quality”, and “policy factors” as the most prevalent constraints that “make it harder to plan or implement” climate action whereas violent conflict is found to constitute a major driver of vulnerability (Pörtner et al., 2022). Critically, political institutions and violent conflict are strong co-determinants of policy adoption and its effective implementation in climate change mitigation and adaptation (Andrijevic, Crespo Cuaresma, Muttarak, et al., 2020; de Groot et al., 2022). Political factors also shape major drivers of the challenges to mitigation and adaptation, such as economic development or demographic changes (Knutsen, 2021;

Acemoglu et al., 2019), as well as vulnerability to climate change (Berrang-Ford et al., 2019). By identifying how political development affects climate change and the conditions of effective policy implementation, political science research is poised to make important contributions towards more realistic climate scenarios and assessments (Brutschin & Andrijevic, 2022). Since existing scenarios do not consider the political feasibility of different pathways, their usability for policy makers is limited (Beck & Oomen, 2021).

Characteristics of political regimes (e.g., extent of democracy) are often overlooked in climate research even though they profoundly shape how accountable political decision-makers are and to whom and thereby which collectively binding decisions are taken. Some argue that unconstrained (autocratic) executives are better placed to achieve radical transformations toward sustainability (Gilley, 2012; Beeson, 2018). While that might be true in some instances, dissemination of accurate information through free civil societies and media (Li & Reuveny, 2006; Carayannis et al., 2021; Levy, 2021) allows for pressure for more ambitious and inclusive policy (Sonnenfeld & Taylor, 2018; Buzogány et al., 2022). Greater respect for civil liberties has a consistent reductive effect on greenhouse gas emissions as well as (non-renewable) energy use (von Stein, 2022). Free and fair elections increase mitigation policy adoption because the electorate is often more concerned over environmental and climate issues than elites (Fiorino, 2018). Thus, high levels of “vertical” accountability to a broad section of the population lead to more ambitious climate policies and laws (Hickmann et al., 2022; Bättig & Bernauer, 2009; Böhmelt et al., 2016; Fiorino, 2011); greater CO₂ emission reductions (Tørstad et al., 2020); less air pollution (Bernauer & Koubi, 2009); improved marine environments (Sjöstedt & Jagers, 2014); and ecosystem vitality (Carayannis et al., 2021).

Institutional capacity (e.g., ‘good governance’, absence of corruption) varies independently from political regime type (Fukuyama, 2014), influencing climate policy adoption, implementation, and effectiveness (Povitkina, 2018; Shukla & Skea, 2023; Brutschin & Andrijevic, 2022). Higher enforcement capacity is ensuring more effective implementation of climate legislation (Eskander & Fankhauser, 2020); progress on renewable energy deployment (Aklin & Urpelainen, 2013; Cherp et al., 2021); phasing out of coal (Jewell et al., 2019); and effective carbon pricing (Levi et al., 2020).

Finally, violent conflict (within or between states) cripples economic activity and livelihoods, deters long-term investments, damages or destroys critical infrastructure, compromises food security and wellbeing, and generates large-scale forced displacement – all impairing a society’s ability to mitigate and to adapt to climate hazards (Buhaug & Uexkull, 2021; Gates et al., 2012; Ujunwa et al., 2019). Armed conflicts often have notable regional spillover effects thus extending these challenges far beyond the battlefields.

Figure 1 visualizes these links. Institutional features characterized by high path dependency and gradual change (e.g., democracy, state capacity), are easier to build into scenarios than stochastic, disruptive events (coup d’état; outbreak of conflict), even if it is also possible to make informed judgments about the likelihood of political disruptions on the basis of structural scenario characteristics.

FIGURE 1. Stylized summary: Influence of domestic political development on climate action

Note: *Political regime characteristics* refer to the domestic rules regulating how collectively binding political decisions are taken and whether political decision-makers can be held accountable. *Institutional quality* refers to the capacity to implement political decisions. *Violent conflict* refers to the breakdown of peaceful sociopolitical relations. *Global governance* is the international dimension that is partly a function of national and intergovernmental institutions and partly of interstate relations (e.g., geopolitical tensions).

3. NEED FOR BETTER INTEGRATION OF POLITICAL DEVELOPMENT INTO CLIMATE SCENARIO FRAMEWORKS

The use of scenarios to understand how GHG emissions, energy and land use, climate risks, and climate action evolve as a function of socioeconomic development and policies (Nakicenovic & Swart R, 2000), forms the backbone of the IPCC assessment process. The framework consists of up to three components: emissions (Representative Concentration Pathways, RCPs), economic and demographic development (the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways, SSPs) and policy developments (the Shared Policy Assumptions, SPAs). They are brought together by integrated assessment models (IAMs) and applied in other impact models. The scenarios are in principle aiming to depict internally consistent combinations of economic, technological, social, and general "governance" elements and global environmental change (van Vuuren et al., 2017).

An increasing number of studies highlight the need to systematically integrate insights from political science and related fields into the SSPs (Brutschin & Andrijevic, 2022; Cherp et al., 2018; Peng et al., 2021; de Bruin et al., 2022).³ At present, narratives underpinning the SSPs only describe political factors in the aggregate for selected development pathways. The lack of conceptual consistency and coherence of political development is apparent in the more detailed descriptions of the narratives (Andrijevic, Crespo Cuaresma, Lissner, et al., 2020).⁴ Tellingly, the scenario framework does not engage with leading political science research on institutional determinants of policymaking and implementation, even though the SSPs are defined on the basis of assumptions about challenges to adaptation and mitigation. Since political factors do not feature systematically in the SSP narratives, they also have not been operationalized and incorporated in the quantitative projections of the SSPs, which instead are limited to socioeconomic and demographic indicators. In IAMs and other models only transparent and quantified assumptions are of consequence (Dixson-Declève et al., 2022). Hence, SSPs do not sufficiently reflect the "real world" plausibility of the underlying socioeconomic scenarios from existing trends and potentially overestimate the feasibility of future climate action.

The SSP scenario framework tacitly assumes that political factors will not shape socioeconomic development or future climate change adaptation and mitigation. However, analyses reveal that SSP projections tend to break markedly from recent trends in socioeconomic development, especially for

low-income countries, where the absence of political factors results in economic development trajectories that far exceed past growth (e.g. Buhaug & Vestby, 2019). Figure 2 shows that modeling future political outcomes as a function of the SSPs also result in projections that in most cases fall outside the range of historical global characteristics. Rule of law projections (Figure 2A) indicate a slight improvement in global average conditions even in SSP3, thus signifying a better situation than what has been the case for most of recent history. The same pattern is found for effectiveness of governance (Figure 2B) while projections of violent conflict (Figure 2C) reveal greater variation, with SSP3–SSP4 entailing a rise in conflict (due to sustained high population growth), whereas SSP1–SSP2 and SSP5 involve declining conflict risk. Given that the SSPs are intended to cover a broad space of possible societal futures, it is striking that the quantified core SSP projections do not enable projections of political institutions and governance that entail worse global aggregate outcomes than observed in recent history.

FIGURE 2. Examples of existing quantifications of political factors along the SSPs

Note: Historical and projected global mean scores for (a) rule of law (Soergel et al., 2021); (b) governance (Andrijevic, Crespo Cuaresma, Muttarak, et al., 2020); and (c) conflict rate (Petrova et al., 2023).

The Shared Policy Assumptions (SPAs) (Kriegler et al., 2014) and policy decision models (Bi et al., 2023) are exceptions. However, they address the content of specific *policies* rather than institutions (*polities*) and processes (*politics*). As such, the current SPAs implicitly assume perfect configurations of political institutions and absence of conflict for each set of policy content (see Box 1).

BOX 1: Three dimensions of the political: From policy to politics and polity

Political development needs to be refined in scenarios, which requires to recognize the three dimensions of the political (Sternberg, 1978) and to go beyond governance. To be effective, policy decisions need to be collectively binding and enforceable. For example, capable design of climate policy (Howlett & Mukherjee, 2014) is a necessary but not a sufficient condition for successful policy making (McConnell, 2010). Therefore, policy studies emphasize the linkages between *policy*, institutions (*polity*), and processes (*politics*):

- *Politics*: Political actors formulate policy through formal (and informal) interactions. Political power shapes those processes.
- *Polity*: Political institutions are rules that shape how individuals and political leaders behave. Laws are legal institutions that regulate politics, define policies, and are the foundation of polities.
- *Policy*: Content and set of instruments adopted to resolve a given problem (e.g., policy for promoting renewable energy can include targets, feed-in tariffs, transfers and subsidies, regulation of grid access, etc.).

These linkages are important prerequisites for effective policymaking. For example, countries may possess sufficient capacity to implement *policies*, but if the public cannot hold the government accountable (*politics*) due to the absence of a democratic *polity*, the effectiveness and inclusiveness of climate action are likely to be poor. Governance – the most commonly used "political concept" in scenario analysis – is an umbrella term that can refer to all of these dimensions, but not necessarily to governmental institutions (e.g., business governance or social networks as governance, etc.). Finally, integrating political factors speaks to current policy debates in global development and climate policy. For instance, states increasingly acknowledge the relevance of political factors for solving common

First steps to integrate insights from political science and related fields into the SSPs (Hughes et al., 2015; Soergel et al., 2021), are summarized in Table 1. Access to displayed indicators and related databases is provided in a data repository (<https://zenodo.org/records/10977219>). The work presented below either projects political development along the SSPs or makes initial attempts to incorporate it. Both approaches suggest that political challenges to climate change mitigation and adaptation are underestimated in the current SSP scenarios.

Most existing **projections of political development along the SSPs** model political factors as outcomes of the quantified variables in the SSPs. They highlight both the feasibility of modeling political factors and the limitations of the preexisting core quantified variables.

Andrijevic et al. (2020) construct the first estimates of governance along the SSPs and statistical relationships between the World Bank's Worldwide Governance Indicators and socioeconomic covariates. Ruhe, Leininger, and Wingens project rule of law as a proxy for the strength of political institutions and violent conflict (Soergel et al., 2021) and evaluate the potential to meet the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Although all selected scenarios show improvements in the

global average of institutional quality and declining global numbers of armed conflict fatalities, they fall short of pre-defined target values for 2030 and 2050 (van Vuuren et al., 2022). Both approaches make strong assumptions but demonstrate the feasibility of modeling political futures.

Hegre et al. (2016) investigates the implications of the core quantified SSPs for armed conflict using a forecasting approach. The strong assumptions of economic convergence in the SSPs imply sustained drops in global conflict occurrence during this century in SSP1 and SSP5 as well as in the middle-of-the-road pathway SSP2. Due to high population growth and weak improvements in education attainment in the Global South, global conflict risk rises somewhat in SSP3-SSP4 relative to 2013, the final year of observed data (but not relative to the current world). A separate analysis concludes that the selection of quantified indicators in the SSPs are too limited for projections of armed conflict futures (Hoch et al., 2021). Recently, use of conflict SSPs suggests that nearly 150 million people will be pushed into poverty by civil wars between 2022-2050 (Moyer, 2023).

Meanwhile, a study on the trade-off between cost-efficiency of climate change mitigation and national sovereignty shows that the unwillingness of countries to build the institutions for international transfers for a just climate change mitigation regime would lead to higher costs for all countries and, therefore, increase the challenges to mitigation (Bauer et al., 2020).

TABLE 1: Examples of indicators of political development (accessible in data repository)

Concept	Indicator	Measurement	Reference (Examples)
Political regime type			
<i>Rule of law</i>	Equality Before the Law and Individual Liberty Index (avail. 1900-2022), derived from V-Dem data (www.v-dem.org ; Coppedge et al., 2023)	Index composed of rigorous and impartial public administration; transparent laws with predictable enforcement; access to justice for men/women; property rights for men/women; freedom from torture; freedom from political killings; forced labor for men/women; freedom of religion; freedom of foreign movement; freedom of	Soergel et al. 2021

		domestic movement for men/women	
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Institutional quality

<i>Government effectiveness</i>	Worldwide Governance Indicators (avail. 1996-2021), derived from the World Bank's World Development Indicators (https://databank.worldbank.org)	Index composed of quality of bureaucracy/institutional effectiveness; excessive bureaucracy; quality of road infrastructure, primary education; satisfaction with public transportation, roads and highways, education system; IPD coverage area (public school, basic health services, drinking water and sanitation, electricity grid, transport infrastructure, maintenance and waste disposal	Andrijevic, Crespo Cuaresma, Muttarak, et al., 2020
<i>Good governance</i>	Worldwide Governance Indicators (avail. 1996-2021), derived from the World Bank's World Development Indicators (https://databank.worldbank.org)	Aggregated index of six governance indicators: voice and accountability; political stability and absence of violence/terrorism; government effectiveness; regulatory quality; rule of law; control of corruption	Andrijevic, Crespo Cuaresma, Muttarak, et al., 2020

Violent conflict

<i>Armed conflict events</i>	Armed conflict events, derived from UCDP Georeferenced Event Dataset (Sundberg & Melander, 2013; Pettersson & Öberg, 2020)	Occurrence of state-based (intrastate) and non-state conflict events	Hoch et al. 2021
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<i>Armed conflict occurrence</i>	Armed civil conflict, derived from Uppsala Conflict Data Program	Occurrence of minor and major armed intrastate conflict	Hegre et al. 2016
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Source: Studies cited in text. Access to data: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10977219>. We exclude public opinion polls or specific sectoral governance mechanisms, as these are more appropriate for national or issue-specific scenarios (Gómez-Sanabria et al., 2020; Guy et al., 2023).

Incorporating political factors in the SSP framework has the potential to provide more realistic projections. For example, a recent study analyzing implications of reaching 1.5°C and 2°C goals by accounting for regional variations in government institutional capacity (Gidden et al., 2023) shows that increasing capacity can address some of the feasibility concerns of overshoot scenarios, and that capacity is more important than the presence of additional carbon removal methods. Work considering the socio-political dynamics of coal phase-out with IAMs shows that despite expansion of coal phase-out pledges to countries with weaker institutions (Vinichenko et al., 2023) and plausible institutional developments in major coal consuming countries (Bi et al. 2023), phasing out coal fast enough to reach climate targets requires much stronger efforts. A recent effort quantified the requisites to overcome political barriers to coal phase-out and calculated the cost of extending such measures to the biggest coal consumers (Nacke et al., 2024). Thus, incorporating political variables is feasible and contribute to making projections more realistic.

In addition, armed conflict has substantial implications for economic performance and is sometimes described as “development in reverse” (Gates et al., 2012; Collier et al., 2003). Petrova et al. (2023) shows that modeling this interactive relationship along the SSPs results in higher armed conflict estimates (see Fig. 2C) and lower GDP trajectories, relative to comparable projections obtained through exogenous modeling (Hegre et al., 2016; Dellink et al. 2017). The International Futures (IFs) model endogenizes country-level governance using domestic governance capacity (Moyer & Bohl, 2017), security, and inclusion (Joshi et al., 2015) and an international relations module that captures patterns of diplomatic exchange (Moyer et al., 2021), economic interdependence, relative material capabilities (Moyer et al., 2023), and the threat of international conflict (Moyer, 2023).

4. OUTLINING A RESEARCH AGENDA FOR INTEGRATING POLITICAL DEVELOPMENT IN CLIMATE SCENARIOS

Work on SSP extensions of political development and integrating them in assessment models is only in its beginnings. Existing projections of political development along the SSPs are based on a simple approach that takes core SSP projections (GDP and population) as given and treats political factors merely as outcomes of socioeconomic developments, similarly to studies of, e.g., hunger (Hasegawa et al., 2015).⁵ However, this is fundamentally different from the call from various modeling communities to systematically integrate political institutions and violent conflict (O'Neill et al., 2020). This requires detailed narrative descriptions of political development pathways and quantitative projections that correspond with these narratives.

Here, we outline a research agenda that responds to this call. It consists of three interlinked elements (groundwork, modification of SSPs, and modification of assessments), illustrated in Figure 3. The agenda identifies tasks and challenges but is not meant to be a practical guidance with detailed instructions. The specifics of models and assessments vary and require individualized treatment.

FIGURE 3: Next steps towards incorporating political factors into scenarios

(I) Groundwork

In a first step, we need validated, solid, systematic, theoretical assumptions of the relationship between political development and climate mitigation and adaptation to enhance the existing SSP framework. A priority should be to move beyond broader and more elusive concepts, such as "good governance", towards specific features of political development using established political science concepts and theory. That requires rigorous, generalizable empirical evidence on, for example, to what extent varying constellations of political regime elements (such as participation, accountability, and rule of law) and institutional quality (such as absence of corruption, capable bureaucracies, and efficient fiscal systems) influence adoption and implementation of climate mitigation and adaptation policies. Operationalization of these specific features into validated, quantified variables that are appropriate for the climate scenario framework follows. A battery of indicators that are standard for quantification in scenarios is a critical element. Political science research already provides such indicators, but continued data collection is necessary to maintain and expand these databases. The data repository of this paper is a first step intended for expansion to a platform providing the data.

This will make political development accessible to the climate modeling communities, including work informing the IPCC's seventh assessment cycle.

The current list includes established indicators to measure political institutions and conflict based on two criteria. First, they are suitable for integration as quantified entities in scenario modeling, i.e., they are measured over long time periods and are comparable across world regions. Second, their inclusion is supported by robust empirical evidence on the drivers of climate change mitigation and adaptation. However, we need more empirical evidence to validate relationships to adaptation, including by means of out-of-sample evaluation and hindsight validation. Identifying new or established indicators that could be projected along the SSPs is another necessary task. For example, new datasets from political science provide those along with quantified measures of uncertainty. They could help to explain variation in country-level vulnerability to climatic hazards, which would be a major advance in the usability of scenarios (Coppedge et al., 2023; Sunberg & Melander, 2013). Integration of qualitative evidence of political development and climate change mitigation and adaptation is also important to ensuring the usability of the extended political scenarios for decision making (Elsawah et al., 2020). This groundwork step informs the following two complementary processes.

(II) Modification of SSPs

Narratives are the basic unit of the SSPs. Adapting or developing new narratives to describe and inform pathways to political futures is needed. By leveraging the quantified variables, the narratives would generate more internal consistency and more clearly defined concepts that are applicable to and facilitate comparison for different regions.

Modeling to extend political development in the SSPs need broadly validated relationships and variables to support further analyses of the implications of political factors for mitigation and adaptation challenges. This is a larger long-term process and a call for the political science and related social science communities. Key tasks in building SSP extensions are the alignment with the SSP-RCP-SPA frame. In addition, scenarios could profit if researchers explored additional SSP scenarios and developed new models. Political development can also be investigated across the full scenario matrix to look at the implications for policy development and effectiveness of outcomes.

(III) Modification of Assessments

Incorporating existing or modified SSP extensions of political development into assessment models needs to be further explored. This should comprise the still understudied analysis of feedback loops into core SSP quantifications. These efforts could include an advanced dynamic simulation setup to account for feedback loops complemented with armed conflict and new socio-economic development projections (Andrijevic, Crespo Cuaresma, Mutarak, et al., 2020; Collier et al., 2003; Hegre et al., 2021). If a climate model would be able to incorporate SSP extensions of political development in a way that they affect model dynamics, one could assess how this changes mitigation and adaptation action in impact assessments or IAMs. A step leading to such a modification should be a model intercomparison project (MIP), *which explores the* benefits of different approaches to modelling and the variability in policy outcomes. However, research teams still need to address the above points before a systematic MIP is possible.

Cross-cutting challenges:

Similar to more general problems in developing SSP scenarios further, accounting for potential climate *feedbacks* into political development will require more sophisticated modelling approaches. Modification of key SSP assumptions include analysis of the strong *assumption of convergence* of economic and, by extension, political institutions in the SSPs; capturing political *uncertainties* relevant to adaptation and mitigation should increase standardization efforts; and scenarios with political factors must be able to address different *scales* (from global to local) and to make credible references to different local contexts.

5. ENGAGING POLITICAL SCIENCE IN CLIMATE FUTURES

The SSP scenarios contain implicit and explicit assumptions about political development, but these are limited, consistency with other parts of the scenarios is lacking, and the assumptions are only weakly linked to associated concepts and established theories in political science and related fields. Most importantly, they have not been quantified to enable researchers to account for, and explore implications of, alternative political contexts when modelling future mitigation trajectories and climate-driven risks. Existing extensions of the SSPs demonstrate that political challenges to climate change mitigation and adaptation are likely underestimated in the current SSP scenarios. This paper provides

a conceptual grounding and associated research agenda on where and what to improve and how to incorporate political development in future climate scenarios, with the hopes that political factors play a more prominent role in the next round of climate assessments. Political science and related research need to engage more and provide important insights that can help with this scenario framework development. For the ambitious research agenda suggested here, however, the research community that develops scenarios of political development needs to expand. Given the importance of marshalling the best scientific evidence to evaluate climate futures, this call should serve as the basis for creating a broader community studying political futures as part of a broader scenario framework.

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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Notes

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² There is a long tradition of political scenario analysis. For example, Shell's scenario work in the 1970s focused on assessing how different political developments would affect the oil market (Cornelius et al., 2005).

³ While only first steps have been made in exploring political implications of the SSPs, a number of recent studies offer extensions of core quantified elements, including health systems (Sellers & Ebi, 2018), extreme poverty (Crespo Cuaresma et al., 2018), and gender equality (Andrijevic, Crespo Cuaresma, Lissner, et al., 2020). The SSPs Extension Explorer gives an overview of relevant extensions (<https://iiasa.ac.at/models-tools-data/shared-socioeconomic-pathway-ssp-extensions-explorer>).

⁴ For example, SSP1 ("Taking the Green Road") suggests that climate mitigation and adaptation is easier if collaboration through multi-level governance is achieved. SSP3 leaves out governance and focuses on conflict and type of political regime ('nationalist', 'authoritarian governments'). SSP4 turns to inequality and concentration of power focusing on social tensions. All of which are relevant political factors but presented in a way that they cannot be compared across scenarios.

⁵ In addition, agent-based-models that measure contingent political factors have been used by modeling communities for national scenarios (Davidson et al., 2024).

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Further Reading

An overview of indicators and data outlined in this text can be found [here](#); for an overview of the quantitative elaborations of the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways see the visualizations on the [SSP Extensions Explorer](#).